

Prediction of Aftershock Characteristics Based on Earthquake Mainshock

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Abstract

This study proposes an algorithm to generate mainshock-aftershock sequence based on the PEER-NGA-West2 database. The results show that all mainshock magnitude, significant duration, mainshock Arias Intensity are statistically greater than those of aftershock at the level of significance $\alpha=1\%$, and the mechanism of a mainshock can be very different from that of an aftershock. In addition, we develop and compare eight prediction models for aftershock magnitude, significant duration, and mechanism, respectively, based on multiple techniques including data partition, transform variable, variable selection, regression, decision tree, neural network, and model comparison. The results indicate that the decision tree is the best tool to predict aftershock magnitude, significant duration, and mechanism for a given mainshock, respectively.

Key Words: Aftershock, Mainshock, Earthquake, Ground motion Characteristics

1. Introduction

A large earthquake can trigger a series of smaller earthquakes (i.e., aftershocks) around the epicenter of the first large earthquake (i.e., mainshock) because of the complex stress interaction of tectonic plates surrounding displaced fault planes after a mainshock. Aftershocks have the potential to pose a significant risk to life safety, cause further structural damage, hinder the reuse and repair of buildings, and increase economic losses, especially when buildings suffer to a certain level of damage during the mainshock (Li et al., 2014; Song, 2014; Song et al., 2014, 2016). In addition, the aftershock characteristics have great impact on collapse risk of post-mainshock buildings (Song et al., 2014).

Using a vast collection of ground motion records across worldwide, this study aims to explore the relationships of ground motion characteristics between mainshock and its largest aftershock and develop prediction models of ground motion characteristics of aftershocks given the seismic information of a mainshock.

2. Methods

2.1 Building Mainshock-Aftershock Sequences

This study uses the Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center (PEER) Next Generation Attenuation (NGA) West2 (shallow crustal earthquake in active tectonic regimes) ground motion database (<https://peer.berkeley.edu/peer-strong-ground-motion-databases>) to collect the information of historical earthquake records. The PEER curates a vast collection of ground motion records from around the world. Currently, the total record number in the NGA-West2 ground motion database is 21,540, of which 1,657 are missing or removed. Thus, the number of available ground motion records is 19,882. However, the PEER NGA West2 database only provides individual Earthquake information and does not distinguish between mainshocks and aftershocks. To

investigate the mainshock-aftershock (MSAS) sequence features, this study builds the MSAS sequence using the following steps:

- (1) Identify unique stations, and search records for each unique station.
- (2) Sort records by year if a specified station has more than one record.
- (3) For a given year, select record with the largest magnitude as mainshock, and select records with magnitude smaller than MS magnitude and occurring within one year after the MS as aftershocks.
- (4) Create MSAS sequences for the given year by combining mainshock and aftershocks.
- (5) Repeat the above procedures to create MSAS sequence for different years and different stations.

This study constructs a sequence consisting of one mainshock and one maximum aftershock. In this study, 2686 MSAS sequences are created. The variables of seismic record used in this study include 5-75% Duration (sec, i.e., significant duration), 5-95% Duration (sec), Arias Intensity (m/sec), Magnitude, the Type of Fault Mechanism (i.e., Strike-Slip, Normal, Normal-Oblique, Reverse, Reverse-Oblique), the Joyner-Boore distance to rupture R_{jb} (km), the closest distance to rupture plane R_{rup} (km), the average shear velocity of top 30 m V_{s30} (m/sec), and the period of the velocity pulse T_p (sec).

2.2 Techniques for Analysis

This study uses multiple techniques for developing prediction models of ground motion characteristics of aftershocks, including data partition, transform variable (TR), variable selection (VS), regression (Reg), decision tree (DT), neural network (NN), and model comparison. We set the mainshock characteristics as predictors to predict aftershock magnitude, significant duration, and mechanism, respectively. In data partition, we use the 50/30/20 allocations for creating training/validation/test data set. In transform variable, we use maximum correlation for interval inputs, and group rare levels for class inputs. In variable selection, we use R-square target model for the class variable: aftershock mechanism. In regression model, the regression type is linear regression for interval variable and logistic regression (Logit) for class variable. We select the stepwise (Step) in the selection model, and select validation error (ValEr) and Schwarz information criterion (SBC) as selection criterion, respectively. In decision tree model, for interval variable and class variable, we use the average square error (ASE) and misclassification rate (Mis) as the assessment measure to select best tree, use validation data for pruning the tree to an optimal size, use probability of ANOVA test (ProF) and probability of Chi-square test (ProbChisq) as the splitting rule, respectively. We also use the Bonferroni adjustment to the p-value. In Neural Network, we select the multiplayer perceptron (MP) as architecture. In model comparison, we use the test data to select the best model.

3. Results

3.1 Relationships of characteristics between mainshock and its following aftershock

We conduct the paired t-test to check if the mainshock magnitude is greater than aftershock magnitude. The results provide strong evidence that mainshock magnitude is statistically greater than aftershock magnitude at the level of significance $\alpha = 1\%$. The mean difference is 0.482. We also find that not only mainshock significant duration is statistically greater than those of aftershock, but also mainshock Arias Intensity is statistically greater than those of aftershock at the level of significance $\alpha = 1\%$. In addition, the results show that the Mechanism of mainshock can be very different from those of aftershock.

3.2 Prediction of aftershock characteristics given a mainshock

We develop eight prediction models for aftershock magnitude, significant duration, and mechanism, respectively. The comparison results of prediction models based on the test data are shown in Table 1. For the prediction of aftershock magnitude, the decision tree model without transform variables is selected as the best model because it has the lowest average squared error of 0.04116 for test data.

The best model to predict aftershock magnitude is shown in Figure 1. The most important variable is mainshock magnitude, followed by Rjb_km, and Mechanism of mainshock.

For the prediction of aftershock significant duration, the decision tree model with transform variables is selected as the best model because it has the lowest average squared error of 714.914 for test data. The best model is shown in Figure 2. The most important variable is the mainshock 5-75% duration, followed by the transformed mainshock 5-95% duration, and the transformed mainshock magnitude.

For the prediction of aftershock mechanism, the decision tree model without transform variables is selected as the best model because it has the lowest Misclassification rate of 0.1577 for test data. The best model to predict aftershock magnitude is shown in Figure 3. The most important variable is mainshock magnitude, followed by Mechanism of mainshock.

Figures 1-3 indicate that the decision tree is the best tool to predict aftershock magnitude, significant duration, and mechanism for a given mainshock, respectively.

Table 1: Comparison of prediction models of aftershock magnitude, duration, and mechanism, respectively.

Aftershock Magnitude		Aftershock Significant Duration		Aftershock Mechanism	
Prediction Model	Test: ASE	Prediction Model	Test: ASE	Prediction Model	Test: Mis
DT(ProbF,ASE)	0.0412	DT(TR,VS,ProbF,ASE)	714.914	DT(ProbChisq,Mis)	0.1577
DT(TR,VS,ProbF,ASE)	0.0500	NN(TR,VS,MP,AVE)	730.520	DT(TR,VS,ProChisq,Mis)	0.1577
NN(MP,AVE)	0.0632	Reg(TR,VS,Step,SBC)	741.110	NN(TR,VS,MP,Mis)	0.2746
Reg(TR,VS,Step,SBC)	0.0705	Reg(TR,VS,Step,ValEr)	741.110	Reg(TR,VS,Logit,Step,Mis)	0.3098
Reg(TR,VS,Step,ValEr)	0.0705	DT(ProbF,ASE)	757.524	Reg(TR,VS,Logit,Step,SBC)	0.3210
Reg(Step,SBC)	0.2023	NN(MP,AVE)	990.488	Reg(Logit,Step,Mis)	0.7681
Reg(Step,SBC)	3.1552	Reg(Step,SBC)	990.590	NN(MP,Mis)	0.7699
NN(TR,VS,MP,AVE)	3.1558	Reg(Step,SBC)	990.758	Reg(Logit,Step,SBC)	0.7699

Figure 1: Best Prediction model of aftershock magnitude: DT(ProbF,ASE)

Figure 2: Best prediction model of aftershock significant duration: DT(TR,VS,ProbF,ASE)

Figure 3: Best prediction model of aftershock Mechanism: DT(ProbChisq,Mis)

4. Conclusions

This study proposes an algorithm to generate mainshock-aftershock sequence and 2686 mainshock-aftershock sequences are created based on the PEER-NGA-West2 database. We observe that the larger mainshock magnitude tends to cause the larger aftershock magnitude and the mechanism of mainshock may be very different from those of aftershock. In addition, we adopt multiple techniques to build prediction models of ground motion characteristics of aftershocks given the seismic information of a mainshock. We find that the decision tree is the best tool to predict aftershock magnitude, significant duration, and mechanism for a given mainshock, respectively.

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